

TOWARDS A HYBRID MODEL OF AN AUTOMATED DECEPTION DETECTION FOR FAKE NEWS: INTELLIGENT FILTERING BASED ON NETWORK PROPERTIES AND BEHAVIOR

Zaitul Iradah binti Mahid Selvakumar Manickam Shankar Karuppayah

October 30, 2018

Abstract

The purpose of a fake news detection is to utilize technologies that will provide the users with the tools and functions to identify and verify information of news in the network that is intentionally deceptive. This paper proposes an automated hybrid deception detection mechanism highlighting on knowledge-based approach from content-based method that focuses on the knowledge network properties and behaviour for the classification tasks, complimented with social context-based methods that utilize auxiliary information from different perspectives in order to further improve the detection accuracy. The proposed work leverages upon structured data repositories (knowledge bases) for computational fact-checking by mining the connectivity pattern on the knowledge graph where false or deception form of a statement can be extracted and analyzed alongside the collective knowledge of the existing knowledge networks. Structured data repositories are data that has been neatly organized into formatted repositories; enabled for easy access and management where elements can be made addressable for effective processing and analysis. The utilization of social context-based approach in the hybrid mechanism will enable an accurate deception detection and at the same time will enable the incorporation of the trust dimension from the

credible repositories. This proposed work is expected to contribute towards minimizing the proliferation of misinformation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fake news on social media has become an important and challenging issue to a lot of parties. It is a serious issue to be dealt by the public and has become one of the crucial problem in the news industry. It has drawn attention and become topic of discussion from the academic side as well. The growing concern on fake news makes sense, considering rapid growth of the Internet and the increase use of computer mediated communication (CMC) technologies such as blogs, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp and other social network, where large scale of news and information can be disseminated to mass audience in the most convenient and fastest way. At the comfort of the wide Internet connectivity, some news or information may be manipulated by some parties to influence public opinions and perceptions with the motivation to gain benefit from it - be it political, social or financial gain [1]. Even so, social media platforms has become the main news sources for many; engaging the users with possible contents of true or fake ones from real journalist and non-journalist with most of the news and information shared via social network are seldom verified [1].

As fake news issue has drawn great attention from the academic side as well, more works on fake news detection mechanisms are conducted recently to counter the problem. However, developing a fake news detection mechanism on social media is ever challenging efforts. As shown in many of the researches, a deception detection requires reliable veracity assessment techniques, as ferreting out deceptive cues from the dubious content with diverse topics and styles, is technically challenging considering false information usually contains deliberate deception and implicit ambiguity of language [2], [3]. These characteristics of fake news made it very linguistically and technically demanding to be understood, interpreted, extracted and analyzed [4], [5]. In addition, exploiting additional information such as the knowledge base is also required as to enhance the deception prediction, although acquiring the quality data can be critical as data verification by existing knowledge repositories may be lacking due to insufficient of authenticated evidences [4]. On the other hand, fake news detection mechanism also needs to mine and exploit the additional information of the social context features derived from the social engagement in the network, particularly of the news consumption on the online communication platforms as these additional information would be essential and useful to enhance the prediction of fake news [6]–[9]. However, mining these additional information may be demanding since users’ social engagements with fake news yield vast, partial and unstructured data [6].

Most existing works on fake news detection on social media arise from different approaches of deception detection, some are even tailored to one distinct method [5], [10]. These detection mechanisms or models mostly emphasize on techniques ranging from those that are strictly content-based to approaches that are social context-based, and few on hybrid-based. The content-based detection mechanism highlights

on the linguistic cue approaches [11] and visual-based approaches [12]. On the other hand, the social context-based detection techniques [5] highlight on users’ social engagement analysis, involving the utilization of relevant social context of the news consumption on social media. Hybrid-based detection method is a combination of techniques from content-based method and social context-based method, utilizing auxiliary information from different perspectives [13].

The utilization of knowledge-based approach is used to check for truthfulness of claims in a news article by querying existing knowledge networks, or publicly available structured data, such as DBpedia ontology, or the Google Relation Extraction Corpus (GREC) etcetera [10] and is seen as better choice for scalable fact-checking method. Existing fact-checking approaches are categorized as expert-oriented, crowdsourcing-oriented, and computational-oriented. Expert-oriented fact-checking is intellectually demanding and time-consuming process since it depends on human experts to investigate relevant data and documents to verify the claims. This somehow is not effective and unable to accommodate for large scale of data veracity [4]. Crowdsourcing-oriented fact-checking involve participation of public “investigator” of normal people to use their wisdom to interpret news content which then are aggregated to produce an overall validity evaluation of the news. On the other hand, computational-oriented fact-checking method seems to be more promising as the approach aims to provide an automated scalable system to classify true and false claims to solve major issues such as identifying check-worthy claims and discriminating the validity of fact claims. [4], [14].

2 PROPOSED WORK

The proposal is to develop an automated hybrid fake news detection mechanism with the highlight of computational filtering technique for classification tasks based on the knowledge network properties and behavior. The hybrid-based detection mechanism has emerged as an alternative to the existing works that are mostly tailored solutions of specific characteristic which has restricted the performance of the techniques [5], [15], [16]. Work by [5], [13] shows that by combining techniques from the content-based and social context-based, a more accurate and automated prediction could be expected. In this proposed work as illustrated in Figure 1 suggests the classification of news article/content as in (1) is done as link prediction task between nodes in the knowledge graph by applying proximity scoring algorithm based on shortest path function. We also propose model to capture fake news characteristics of user's engagement involving source/publisher as in (2) and user as in (3) of the news consumption. These features capture the temporal behaviors of user's activity and response, and produce score vector. All three outputs from (1), (2) and (3) are concatenated and the resultant vector is used for classification.

This proposed work aims (a) to classify the information of the news in the network whether it belongs to truthful or deceptive classification; (b) to evaluate the accuracy of the computational fact checking technique and link prediction using knowledge graph for the proximity of truth or deception; and (c) to develop a hybrid deception detection mechanism focussing on filtering technique based on the network properties and behaviour for the classification tasks. The expected outcomes from this proposed work is that there will be a significant improvement in terms of

accuracy in predicting fake news hence contribute to minimizing the proliferation of misinformation.

Figure 1 Proposed Framework for Automated Hybrid Fake News Detection Mechanism

References

- [1] E. C. Tandoc, Z. W. Lim, and R. Ling, "Defining 'Fake News': A typology of scholarly definitions," *Digital Journalism*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 1–17, 2017.
- [2] S. Feng, R. Banerjee, and Y. Choi, "Syntactic stylometry for deception detection," *Proc. 50th Annu. Meet. Assoc. Comput. Linguist. Short Pap. 2. Assoc. Comput. Linguist.*, no. July, pp. 171–175, 2012.
- [3] M. Potthast, J. Kiesel, K. Reinartz, J. Bevendorff, and B. Stein, "A Stylometric Inquiry into Hyperpartisan and Fake News," no. February, 2017.
- [4] K. Shu, A. Sliva, S. Wang, J. Tang, and H. Liu, "Fake News Detection on Social Media: A Data Mining Perspective," *Proc. 25th ACM Conf. Hypertext Soc. media - HT '14*,

- pp. 316–317, 2017.
- [5] N. Ruchansky, S. Seo, and Y. Liu, “CSI: A Hybrid Deep Model for Fake News Detection,” in *Software, Telecommunications and Computer Networks (SoftCOM), 2012 20th International Conference on*, 2017, no. SoftCOM, pp. 1–6.
- [6] J. Tang, Y. Chang, and H. Liu, “Mining Social Media with Social Theories: A Survey,” *SIGKDD Explor. Newsl*, 2014.
- [7] L. Wu and H. Liu, “Tracing Fake-News Footprints: Characterizing Social Media Messages by How They Propagate,” *Proc. Elev. ACM Int. Conf. Web Search Data Min. - WSDM ’18*, pp. 637–645, 2018.
- [8] S. M. Jang *et al.*, “A computational approach for examining the roots and spreading patterns of fake news: Evolution tree analysis,” *Comput. Human Behav.*, 2018.
- [9] M. Lai, D. I. Hernández Fariás, V. Patti, and P. Rosso, “Friends and enemies of clinton and trump: Using context for detecting stance in political tweets,” in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2017.
- [10] N. J. Conroy, N. J. Conroy, V. L. Rubin, and Y. Chen, “Automatic Deception Detection: Methods for Finding Fake News,” 2015, no. October.
- [11] M. . American Society for Information Science and Technology. Annual Meeting (78th : 2015 : Saint Louis, A. S. Grove, and Y. American Society for Information Science and Technology, “Automatic deception detection: methods for finding fake news,” in *Proceedings of the 78th ASIS&T Annual Meeting: Information Science with Impact: Research in and for the Community*, 2015.
- [12] Z. Jin, J. Cao, Y. Zhang, J. Zhou, and Q. Tian, “Novel Visual and Statistical Image Features for Microblogs News Verification,” *IEEE Trans. Multimed.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 598–608, 2017.
- [13] K. Shu, S. Wang, and H. Liu, “Exploiting Tri-Relationship for Fake News Detection,” no. July, 2017.
- [14] N. Hassan, C. Li, and M. Tremayne, “Detecting Check-worthy Factual Claims in Presidential Debates,” in *Proceedings of the 24th ACM International on Conference on Information and Knowledge Management - CIKM ’15*, 2015.
- [15] Y. Chen, N. J. Conroy, and V. L. Rubin, “Misleading Online Content,” in *Proceedings of the 2015 ACM on Workshop on Multimodal Deception Detection - WMDD ’15*, 2015, no. November, pp. 15–19.
- [16] V. Rubin, “News Verification Suite: Towards System Design to Supplement Reporters’ and Editors’ Judgements,” in *Proceedings of the 45th Annual Conference of The Canadian Association for Information Science/ L’Association canadienne des sciences de l’information (CAIS/ACSI2017)*, 2017, no. May.